

ARCHITECTURE

CULTURAL HERITAGE OF AZERBAIJAN IN THE UNESCO WORLD HERITAGE LIST

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Abstract

The Republic of Azerbaijan was admitted to UNESCO on June 3, 1992. The aim is to preserve the historical and cultural heritage and present it to the whole world. Today, relations between Azerbaijan and UNESCO are stable. The inclusion of the material and spiritual heritage of Azerbaijan in the UNESCO list of rare works is a key indicator of international cooperation. Inclusion of the "Baku State Historical and Architectural Reserve Icheri Sheher, including the Palace of the Shirvanshahs and the Maiden Tower", "Gobustan Rock Historical and Artistic Landscape Complex", "Palace of Sheki Khans and Sheki Historical Center" in the UNESCO World Heritage List and the inclusion of the Historical, "Cultural Landscape of Khinalig and Migration Route" on the Tentative List of the UNESCO World Heritage Committee in 2023 is an important event of our culture and emphasizes the continuity of cooperation between Azerbaijan and this organization.

Keywords: UNESCO, Azerbaijan, World Heritage, Icheri Sheher State Historical-Architectural Reserve, Gobustan Rock Historical-Artistic Landscape Complex, Sheki Khan Palace and Sheki Historical Center, "Cultural Landscape of Khinalig and Migration Route".

Conclusion: The inclusion of the rich historical and architectural heritage of Azerbaijan in the list of UNESCO monuments with an enhanced protection regime is a high assessment of this heritage by the international community.

Introduction. UNESCO is an important tool for transferring the culture of every nation to the world. As an influential international organization, it has ample opportunities for mutual cooperation and integration of different countries. At present, the state of Azerbaijan is also represented in UNESCO, which unites 195 countries. The goal is to preserve the history and cultural heritage of Azerbaijan and present it to the world. The Republic of Azerbaijan was admitted to UNESCO membership on June 3, 1992. Since 1993, the parties have been discussing issues of expanding cooperation and long-term plans for its further development. Azerbaijan's extensive cooperation with UNESCO in the field of education, science and culture paved the way for the integration of our country into world civilization, the promotion of our national culture and, most importantly, closer recognition of our people in the world. Thanks to this organization, the ancient and rich culture of Azerbaijan rose from the national to the international level and became part of the world culture. In 1972, UNESCO adopted the Convention concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage. One of the main activities of UNESCO is the protection of historical and cultural monuments. Today, relations between Azerbaijan and UNESCO are steadily implemented. The inclusion of the material and spiritual heritage of Azerbaijan in the UNESCO list of rare works is a key indicator of international cooperation. Inclusion of the state historical and architectural reserve of Icheri Sheher, including the palace of the Shirvanshahs and the Maiden Tower, the Gobustan rock historical and artistic landscape complex, the palace of the Sheki khans and the Sheki reserve "Yukharibash" in the UNESCO World Heritage List, Inclusion of Azerbaijani mugam

in the list of masterpieces of material cultural heritage, as well as ashug, tar art and the Novruz holiday on the UNESCO Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity are important events for our culture and emphasize the continuity of cooperation between Azerbaijan and this organization.

Methodology: Obtaining information about monuments by conducting research in nature reserves and using scientific literature.

Azerbaijan has rich immovable historical and cultural monuments. There are 6308 registered monuments in the country, of which 65 are registered as universal, 2034 as country-specific, 4209 as local monuments. A number of monuments, complexes and settlements are registered by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan as 26 historical and cultural reserves [2]. The protection and use of monuments is reflected in a number of decrees and orders of the President. Today, 3 historical and cultural reserves on the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan are included in the "UNESCO World Heritage List", and one is included in the preliminary UNESCO list for consideration as a reserve. The main purpose of the study is to present to the world the historical monuments included in the UNESCO World Heritage List, presenting their history, heritage of urban planning and architecture. The novelty of the research lies in the fact that, for the first time, in the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan, three reserves included in the UNESCO World Heritage List are presented together.

The Baku State Historical and Architectural Reserve Icheri Sheher, including the Palace of the Shirvanshahs and the Maiden Tower, are located in the south of the Absheron Peninsula, on the shores of the Caspian Sea bay, well protected from wind and storms. This port city played a key role in the development of trade relations with foreign countries. The Caspian Sea became a key factor in the formation of the urban structure of ancient Baku and played a key

role in the cultural, material and economic life of the population. Icheri Sheher is a valuable urban monument of Azerbaijan, like Baku. The Muslim urban structure, typical of the entire Middle East, led to the development of Baku with a three-part planning composition. Icheri Sheher is an urban part of ancient Baku that has survived to this day. Despite its small size (22 hectares), Icheri Sheher was an ideal Muslim city in terms of layout and spatial structure [3].

Ancient Icheri Sheher, which is over 2000 years old, was built on the sloping southeastern slope of a high hill. The fact that Baku is an important port city is reflected in the fact that its shopping center is formed as a wide street running parallel to the coastline. The city plan, surrounded by two rows of fortified walls, was developed in accordance with the natural landscape. The inner city has practically preserved the quarter system, the formation of which lasted from the Middle Ages to the end of the 19th century. The narrow and crooked pedestrianized streets have created a complex, chaotic planning structure in accordance with the terrain and Muslim lifestyle [5]. The city has 14 geographical, patronomical and professional quarters, formed from the Middle Ages to the 19th century. Due to the arrangement of the blocks in the form of terraces on the hillside, most of the old Baku houses have a view of the sun and the sea. Residential buildings, which have become an integral, important element of micro-districts, were built with a planning composition

corresponding to the small area of the inner city of Baku, geographical, natural and climatic features. For defense purposes, the Shirvanshahs' Palace complex is located on the highest relief of the city.

Surrounded by the walls of the Icheri Sheher castle, for hundreds of years it has acquired a chaotic layout with an intertwined mixed street system, dead ends and valuable monumental buildings. The city is built on the basis of a system of 11 small streets connecting Boyuk (Big) and Kichik (Small) Gala (Fort) Streets, framing in a semicircle the striped shopping street Minaret, small quarter squares, defensive towers and fortress walls, with Gulla (Tower) Street. On an area of 22 hectares of Icheri Sheher, 500 historical and architectural monuments have been registered (Figure 1). Here, defensive, religious, civil, memorial buildings complete the urban composition of the reserve. The Maiden Tower and the Palace of the Shirvanshahs have been included in the UNESCO World Heritage List since 2000. Monuments of international, national and local importance are registered in the Icheri Sheher reserve in the catalog "Distribution of immovable monuments of history and culture taken under state protection in the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan, according to the degree of their importance", approved by Resolution No. 132 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated August 2, 2001 [1].

Figure 1. Historical and Architectural Reserve Icheri Sheher

Maiden's Tower. This is the most majestic, ancient and mysterious monument of the Old City. It is believed that it was built before Islam, but its exact date is unknown. Some researchers attribute it to the period of the (VII-VIII centuries BC), others - to the Sassanid period (VI-VII centuries) [3]. There is no doubt that at that time a temple of fire worshipers was located next to the Maiden Tower, and the tower played a decisive role in the defense system. Its direct purpose remains controversial: a defensive structure, a temple of worshipers' fire, an ancient observatory, etc. The Maiden's Tower was the dominant temple complex in the early period and the main tower of the city's fortress in the Middle Ages. This fortress was not conquered by

the Mongols even in their first powerful campaigns in the 13th century.

In the north, the height of the Maiden Tower is 31 meters, in the south it is 28 meters, the thickness at the base is 5 meters and 4 meters higher, inside it is divided into eight floors. From the second floor to the last floor, the connection is made by a spiral staircase to the thickness of the wall. The diameter of the tower on the ground floor is 16.5 meters. Interpretation of a building, starting from the third floor, dividing its surface into thin horizontal belts with a stone in the form of ribs, volumetric plasticity, unusual solution of its form has no analogues in world architecture.

Figure 2. Maiden's Tower.

The palace complex of the Shirvanshahs. The palace complex of the Shirvanshahs was built for the purpose of protection, on the highest relief of the Old City, on a hill. The ensemble is a masterpiece of Azerbaijani architecture. This ensemble is distinguished by high artistic and architectural qualities, masterful placement of individual volumes in relief, beautiful solution of silhouettes, skillful use of decorative features of local limestone and magnificent stone carving, which made it possible to create a whole stylistic direction in Azerbaijani architecture. The ensemble was formed in the XV-XVI centuries around three small courtyards located at different levels, which ensured the versatility of volumetric solutions. It includes the palace building near the square courtyard, Divan-Khana (15th century), the mausoleum of the

scientist Seyyid Yahya Bakuvi (15th century) in the middle courtyard, the Kei-Gubad mosque (17th century), as well as the Sultan Murad III mosque (1584) consists of a gate. A palace mosque (1441) and a tomb of the Shirvanshahs (1435) - "Tomb" were built in the lower courtyard. Below were built a magnificent hunting lodge and a large palace bath (15th century), which supplied the bath with water. Numerous buildings of the palace complex of the Shirvanshahs with different purposes are located in relief in accordance with their purpose. The palace complex of the Shirvanshahs in Baku is the only architectural example in the Middle East that has been completely preserved since the Middle Ages. (Figure 2) The compositional perfection of each building, precise execution, high skill, beautiful stonework raised the

palace complex to the pinnacle of Azerbaijani architecture. The palace complex of the Shirvanshahs

has been repeatedly restored, baths and hunting grounds in the lower courtyard have been preserved.

Figure 2. The palace complex of the Shirvanshahs

"The cultural landscape of the rock art of Gobustan." The reserve area is 4400 hectares. The monuments of Gobustan, as early settlements, are an invaluable source for studying the past, traditions, roots of the ancient culture and art of the Azerbaijani people, the pre-architectural way of life of the people, the main shelters needed to protect the environment from flora and fauna in the area. The reserve basically occupies a large territory, where three mountains are located - "Boyukdash", "Kichikdash" and "Chingildag" [6]. There are many primitive human camps, ancient settlements, burial mounds and other archaeological sites from the Stone Age to the Middle Ages. Discovered 20 ancient sites and settlements, more than 30 mounds, about 6000 petroglyphs. A cultural layer and material remains were found in them, indicating life in various historical eras: The Mesolithic in five of them, the Neolithic in four, the bronze in seven, from antiquity in one and in five in the Middle Ages, from the Firuz camp, were found a grave dating back to the Mesolithic era, and from the Kaniza camp a grave from the Neolithic era.

The material and cultural wealth of the Gobustan monument lies in the fact that human life here began in the tenth millennium BC and continued until the 18th century. As a result of archaeological excavations in Gobustan, in the settlements of the Bronze Age, the remains of buildings, tools and household appliances, fragments of ceramics, animal bones, beads from animal bones, 11 human graves dating back to the 3rd and 2nd millennia were discovered. Among other finds

on Kaniza, a stone female figure was found. The finds show that during the Mesolithic, Neolithic and Bronze Age on the territory of Gobustan there were natural conditions suitable for human life, during the Mesolithic and Neolithic periods - hunters and fishermen, and in the Bronze Age - agricultural and cattle breeding tribes. Mesolithic sites and rock shelters have also been found in Gobustan. In Gobustan, the cradle of ancient civilization, not far from the Boyukdash cave, there is a stone tablet with the Latin alphabet, confirming the presence of the Roman emperor Domitiano in the 1st century BC. Rock carvings of Gobustan vary in size, composition and technique of drawing, depending on the period of their engraving. This once again confirms that the petroglyphs belong to different periods [9].

In 1966, the historical territory of Gobustan was declared a nature reserve. In 2007, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan signed Decree No. 2213 of 11.06.2007 "On the protection of historical and cultural values located on the territory of the Gobustan State Historical and Artistic Reserve", and in the same year the Gobustan Historical and Artistic Reserve was included in the List of World Cultural Heritage UNESCO (Figure 3). In the same year, by the Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated November 6, 2007, the Gobustan Reserve was given the status of "National Reserve". The main activity of the reserve is the organization of the study, protection and popularization of petroglyphs, paintings, burial mounds and settlements.

Figure 3. Gobustan State Historical and Artistic Reserve

"The historical center of Sheki together with the Khan's palace." Considering the wealth of monuments, the historical center of Sheki, one of the historical cities of Azerbaijan, has been declared by the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan since 1967 the historical and architectural reserve "Top Point". The 13 quarters of the reserve include the Sheki Khan's palace, religious and civil buildings. The palace of Sheki khans and the house of Sheki khans have their own unique architectural and decorative design, the Upper and Lower caravanserais, a round temple, castle walls, Juma mosque, Omar Efendi mosque, middle Civil buildings, one of the architectural gems of the 20th century - baths Aghvanlar, Dere and Gum, arched bridges across the river - have always attracted the attention of travelers, geographers and tourists since the Middle Ages [7]. Sheki's natural beauty is reflected in all the historical monuments built in the city. All these are features of Sheki architecture. The main streets are divided into narrower, smaller streets, bends and dead ends, depending on the local landscape. Small streets running off the main street surround the city like capillaries separated from the main artery. The urban structure of the reserve, mainly river-oriented, provides easy access to a shopping street, which in turn is one of

the factors necessary for the economic activity of the population [10].

Sheki Khan's palace. One of the masterpieces of the Sheki Khanate is the Sheki Khans' palace. The Shekihanovs' house and the Sheki khans' palace are considered museums of all kinds of works of art of Azerbaijan in the history of artistic culture of the 18th-19th centuries. Here are the best examples of stone carving, network system, stained glass, as well as wall paintings with ornaments and themes. Shabaka (tracery) art occupies a special place in the artistic solution of the interior and exterior of the Sheki Khans' palace. The mesh is a decorative flat surface, assembled from many carved wooden elements and pieces of colored glass fastened between them without glue or nails. The most common shabaka compositions are multi-ray stars. The basis of the artistic image on the shabaka is the contours of sunlight and geometric shapes filtered through colored glass. Sheki Reserve, the third monument of Azerbaijan, included in the list of "Cultural Heritage" by UNESCO in 2019, has already introduced the world to the history and culture of our country, and its protection will be constantly monitored by UNESCO (Figure 4). (In the future, it is planned to renovate the khan's palace and a number of monuments of the reserve.

Figure 4. Sheki Khan's palace

"Cultural Landscape of Khinalig and Migration Route" is the 4th territory of Azerbaijan included in the UNESCO World Heritage List. The World Heritage Site includes the surrounding grasslands (Guba and Gusar) used by the local population, including the village of Khinalig, and the winter areas of the Central Aran region (Absheron and Hajigabul), as well as the historical migration route (Guba-Shamakhi) with a length of more than 200 km between them. -Gobustan) and constitutes the nomadic culture of Khinalig. The Heritage Area included in the UNESCO World Heritage List encompasses a large cultural landscape consisting of a total of 44,829.41 hectares (about 45 thousand hectares) of the Heritage

Area and 109,392.78 hectares (more than 109 thousand hectares) of the Buffer Zone, passing through the territory of 6 administrative districts. does

The area included in the World Heritage list contains examples of material culture such as ancient historical cemeteries of nomads, holy places, piers, historical bridges, and springs.

The nomination "Khinalig and Migration Route Cultural Landscape" has been registered under criteria 3 (iii) and 5 (v) of the World Heritage. The 3rd criterion was presented as an exceptional example of the vertical nomadic culture in which the Khinalig community was historically engaged in nomadic animal husbandry, and the 5th criterion was presented as an exceptional

example of the balance of human-nature relations, the development of the system of eco-social relations in difficult climatic conditions, and the sustainable use of natural resources. In order to protect the importance for the cultural heritage of Azerbaijan, the area where the migration route is located, to create a unified management model and to develop responsible tourism here, on September 4, 2023, by order of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the State History-Culture and Ethnography Reserve was established. The unique landscape of Khinalig village, located at an altitude of 2300 meters above sea level, is reflected in its urban planning and architecture. The village has preserved traditional construction methods, folklore and ethnographic traditions. Written information about the history of the existence of henna can be found in Strabon and his writings in the 1st millennium of our era. The date of establishment of the village is B.C. It dates back to the III-II millennium. The modern

inhabited area of the village used to consist of several small villages located at certain distances from the village. The village of Khinalig, inhabited by the ancient tribes of Caucasian Albania, has its own unique architectural appearance. [11] According to the information given by the local population in these areas, life started in caves and continued with the primitive community structure. According to their religious beliefs, the population went through the stages of paganism, Zoroastrianism, fire worship and Islam. This is proven by the archaeological excavations conducted in the area for several years, and the "Fire" temple near the village. There are medieval Ateshparast temple, Khidir Nabi tomb, Sheikh Shalbuz, Abu Muslim mosques, caves and many archaeological monuments here. The population is engaged in cattle breeding. Since it is not suitable for agriculture, some people are engaged in planting potatoes and onions in the foothills. (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Khinalig State Historical, Architectural and Ethnographic Reserve

Conclusion

The inclusion of the rich historical and architectural heritage of Azerbaijan in the list of UNESCO monuments with an enhanced protection regime is a high assessment of this heritage by the international community. This has become an important factor in acquainting the world with the history of Azerbaijan, its material and cultural samples and, in turn, in the development of international tourism, making historical places attractive to tourists. Because the tourist is interested in the history of the city, as well as the country, material and cultural samples that reflect the way of life. In turn, this region, like any country, its history, its role in the formation of human civilization, its cultural heritage examples brings benefits. Inclusion of the cultural heritage of Azerbaijan in the UNESCO World Heritage List will continue in the near future.

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